

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

In the first regular issue of this year I'd like to take the opportunity to thank all consortium members for their financial and organizational support which makes it possible to keep J.UCS an open access journal for readers and publication fees-free journal for authors. Also I'd like to gratefully acknowledge the authors for the contribution of their novel work and the board of editors for their thorough reviews which are essential to guarantee the high quality of the journal. We are very proud to report that the impact factor has been improved significantly over the last year and has now reached 0.762.

I am very pleased to look back to a very successful year 2013. In 6 regular issues, 40 high quality papers were accepted with an acceptance rate below 20%. 88 papers in 12 special issues have covered various emerging focused topics in computer science. We can report 105, 832 unique visits and approximately 60.000 pdf downloads over the year 2013.

I would be very grateful for suggestions and feedback on how we could even further improve and develop J.UCS in the future. Please do encourage your students and colleagues to submit high-quality articles to our journal. Also, we'd like to further extend our editorial board so if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board.

Another important goal for 2014 is an extension of the J.UCS consortium by further partners from the North American and Asia-Pacific regions; please contact me if you and your organization are interested in joining and supporting J.UCS.

This issue covers 7 papers of various topics in computer science by authors from 6 countries. Carlos Blanco, Ignacio García-Rodríguez de Guzmán, Eduardo Fernández-Medina and Juan Trujillo from Spain discuss in their research work the benefits of applying a model driven architecture for developing secure OLAP applications.

Tarek Chenaina and Abdulaziz Alraddadi from Saudi Arabia introduce their approach applying clustering techniques for identifying fuzzy controllers parameters.

In a collaborative research between Chile and France, Johan Fabry, Romain Robbes and Marcus Denker introduce a domain specific aspect language for extending integrated development environments.

Tomas Grigalis and Antanas Čenys from Lithuania introduce in their approach of unsupervised structured data extraction from template-generated Web pages.

Osman Hasan and Syed Ali Khayam from Pakistan discuss formal linear cryptanalysis using the higher-order logic theorem prover HOL4.

Javier Parapar, David E. Losada and Álvaro Barreiro from Spain combine in their research psycho-linguistic, content-based and chat-based features for detecting suspicious subjects in chat rooms.

Daniel Perez-Gonzalez, Pedro Soto-Acosta and Simona Popa from Spain introduce a virtual learning environment covering communication and interaction barriers for users with special needs.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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